

AIMS AND CONTENTS OF "SHOE TYING" METHOD IN SECONDARY SCHOOL

Umarova Feruza Uralovna

Teacher of English language of School 184, Chilanzar District of Tashkent City

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7454468>

Abstract. *In today's globalized world, language learning is gaining great importance. It is not a secret to anyone that the attention to English language teaching is increasing, especially in our country. Therefore, many favorable conditions are being created in schools for teaching the language. This article describes in detail the method of shoe tying in secondary school.*

Keywords: *method, style, English language, "shoe tying", technique, secondary school, teachers, etc.*

ЦЕЛИ И СОДЕРЖАНИЕ МЕТОДА "ЗАВЯЗКИ ОБУВИ" В СРЕДНЕЙ ШКОЛЕ

Аннотация. *В современном глобализированном мире изучение языков приобретает большое значение. Ни для кого не секрет, что внимание к преподаванию английского языка возрастает, особенно в нашей стране. Поэтому в школах создается много благоприятных условий для обучения языку. В данной статье подробно описан способ завязывания шнурков в общеобразовательной школе.*

Ключевые слова: *метод, стиль, английский язык, «завязывание шнурков», техника, общеобразовательная школа, учителя и др.*

English as a foreign language in secondary school is considered as a new subject for students since some of them are not familiar with it. Furthermore, secondary schools' students need more motivation in learning English, especially in the digital era. Thus, teachers as the motivators should have some sound approaches to teach it. Teaching English in secondary schools is important to give primary knowledge of English to students. Teachers should know what the students are needed in learning English so that teachers can apply appropriate techniques in teaching. "Classroom", a word that brings to our mind a setting wherein a teacher stands in front of a class of 30 to 40 students, delivering a lecture with a specific gravity in his/her voice. This is the method of teaching that was prevalent when we were in school some two decades ago. However, things have changed over the years, and though it was one of the most effective methods of teaching English to young students, it no longer considered the same now. This is due to various reasons, maybe because:

- the present generation gets exposure to the world through social media
- their knowledge base is augmenting by the information available on the internet
- the students nowadays are more impatient and to grab their attention, teaching methods need to cater to their dynamic thinking process.

In teacher learning as a cognitive process, teachers will have experiences to review their beliefs and thoughts about teaching and learning and examine how these influence their instructional decisions in their every classroom practice. Based on the next view, teacher learning as personal construction, teachers are directed to learn through activities which make use of self-awareness and personal interpretation to create a solution for their classroom challenges. Learning activities drawn from the last view of teacher learning encourage teachers to examine their teaching experiences as a critical reflection so that teachers can develop a better understanding of the strength and weakness sides of their teaching practices. In the classroom, teachers need to apply the three levels, which consist of approach, method, and technique. This study employed qualitative case study design in which produces descriptive data. This study focused on describing the pedagogical approach in teaching English in secondary school, methods, the techniques used, and the process of teaching and learning. The research was conducted three months to 30 English teachers of secondary school in Tanjung, Tabalong. To collect the data, the researchers used a questionnaire and interview. A questionnaire is used to find out teachers' approaches, methods, and techniques used in teaching and learning process. Moreover, interview was used to find appropriate information about the teaching and learning process in the classroom.

The newest methods and techniques in teaching English in this era are related to the media which is suitable to be used in different level of students. The choice of instructional media which is appropriate is important to attract students. However, providing media in every learning is a choice, as long as the material is well-delivered to the students. In some cases, the classes which use some media make the students actively participate in the process of teaching and learning. Teachers have preferred the classes in which the students are actively involved so that it will have a good interaction among students. To improve students' spirit and ability, the reward is given when students can answer questions correctly and appropriately. To assess the students, teachers emphasize on an appropriate skill compared to the representation of whole language skills. In the learning which emphasizes on a productive skill such as speaking, the teachers prefer to correct students' mistakes directly rather than postpone them.

Language teaching, like any other topic, has undergone a lot of changes. It has shifted to role-plays, interactive games, short visuals, etc. from the traditional ways, such as lectures by facilitators with only a blackboard to support and spell repetition and grammar worksheets, have shifted to role-plays. Language teaching has its challenges. Most of the time, it is a foreign language that the learner can't pick up from his/her surroundings, and you should teach patiently and systematically so that the students become confident and can read, write and speak the language effortlessly. The English language is the language of the world, and English teachers have changed their methods of delivery over the years to suit the present scenario. In this article, I will be discussing specific popular and efficient ways of teaching the English language, which fulfills the demand of modern learners. This method of teaching English, also known as the direct method, seems to be a response to the Grammar translation technique. In this process, the teacher who is aiming to teach English as a second language, asks the learner to think in English so that they can communicate in English. The technique aims at building a connection between thought and expression. It required the teacher to strictly prohibit the student from using his/her native language. The learner is supposed to perfectly express himself/herself in English, with proper accent and usage of grammatical skills. This method of teaching English is used in modern times and is useful in teaching to communicate in English. As the student thinks and talks in English in

real-life situations, they learn the language accurately, and there is no rote learning or translation. This might take some time, but whatever is learned has a long term effect on our memory. One such method is the shoe tying method. It goes without saying that this method is organized as a game for children in the classroom and serves to convey the necessary information to them. In this method, the teacher plays the main role. He pastes English words of certain forms on the board and organizes a question-and-answer game for students. This method makes it easier to get information of various categories, and it is very convenient and effective for creating a positive atmosphere in the classroom.

REFERENCES:

1. Gromova O.A. Audio-visual method and practice of its application. M., 1977.
2. Domashnev A.I. et al. Methods of teaching English at a pedagogical university. M., 1983.
3. The main directions in the methodology of teaching foreign languages in the XX centuries. / Ed. M.V. Rakhmanova. M., 1972.
4. Palmer G. Oral method of teaching foreign languages. M., 1960.
5. Sheils D. Communicative in teaching modern languages. [Council for Cultural Cooperation. Project No. 12 “Learning and Teaching Modern Languages for Communication Purposes.”] Council of Europe Press, 1995.